

SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES USING THE PRINCIPLE OF COOPERATION BASED ON INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract: This article discusses scientific and pedagogical approaches to the use of cooperation in teaching English lessons based on international experience, and methods incorporating modern pedagogical technologies.

Keywords: Pedagogy, education, upbringing, approach, psychology, adaptation, approach, integration, classification, methodology, statistics, pedagogical technology.

In the world experience, the successful organization of effective teaching of English and the educational process, the study of the experience of the international universities of Cambridge, Georgia (Georgia State University), Algiers and Albania in teaching foreign languages for special purposes, the effectiveness of speech movement in the phenomenon of pragmatic presupposition, the principle of cooperation in the development of languages, pragmatic linguistics, research is carried out on the development and popularization of the language of importance. At the same time, the creation of educational and methodological support of the use of the principle of cooperation in English lessons and the development of proposals and recommendations for determining the level of effectiveness and application in practice, creating methodological manuals that meet the standards and requirements of modern educational standards, improving the didactic possibilities of using the principle of cooperation in the study of foreign experience and English in higher education institutions.

To put it more precisely, the principle of cooperation allows students to learn together in small groups or in pairs, and through this cooperation to effectively master a particular subject or topic. Students are shown in the process of working in a group with a sense of responsibility based on the task assigned to them, to contribute to the success of the group, and thus manifest themselves. When using the "principle of cooperation" in teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to understand the purpose of this principle. In particular:

1. Students' activity in the learning process increases. In the center of the educational process of reciprocal learning, it is possible to create a student-

centered learning environment that ensures the active participation of students from the educational environment based on the provision of information by the teacher or only in the form of lectures. Because, unlike traditional educational technology, which allows you to work only with a small number of students, with the help of this technology you can.

4. Interest in learning a language increases through group achievements. Collaborative language learning technology, working in small groups or pairs, a healthy group competition environment will increase students' interest in language learning. The use of the principle of cooperation in the educational process is based on the following target areas: - the organization of relations based on educational cooperation, with the rejection of pedagogical requirements; - an individual approach to students based on humanistic ideas; - achieving the determination of professional and spiritual unity in the educational process. The expected result of teaching a foreign language on the basis of the principle of cooperation is not only the study of a foreign language by language learners, but also the formation and development of their friendly relations with each other, communicative skills and competencies. The use of the cooperative principle in English lessons is organized within the English language.

Most importantly, they contribute to the development of knowledge, abilities and competencies in the subject of English in students. For example: 1. Taking turns in lessons — during the implementation of the teaching structure, students tell the answers to the question in a circle. 2. One-on-one writing of short answers in a team learning structure – in which students take turns doing writing work. 3. The learning structure used to develop English speaking skills serves to develop critical and creative thinking. At the same time, students will increase their vocabulary and learn from each other in critical and creative thinking or support in expressing ideas that are not similar to each other.

4. During the implementation of the educational structure "Inner and Outer Circle", students form inner and outer circles and share ideas with their colleagues, i.e. classmates. 5. Thinking aloud is a collaborative thinking technique in which teachers and students participate, and is used to solve problems, answer questions, repeat the thought process aloud, and express ideas aloud to each other. These tasks are always taken by students with pleasure and contribute to the development of "learning skills". The principle of cooperatives promotes student interest in English language learning.

As a result of the principle of cooperation, the opportunities for intensifying the educational process will be even wider. The principle of cooperation is a modern person-centered educational approach that allows implementing the requirements of the new generation standards. In the process of teaching English, you need methods that are focused not only on logical thinking, but also on non-standard problem solving. Mastering specific areas of thinking leads to a decrease in brain energy expenditure and an increase in thinking efficiency. Although these disciplines are not currently used, there are methods that can be justified by the principles of cooperation, listed below: – not looking for a solution until you fundamentally study the essence of the problem posed; – teaching to search for solutions of non-standard situations; – preparation of questions that will help to find an answer to the problem for which you are looking for a solution; – search for different ways to achieve the goal, and then choose the optimal one; – draw up an approximate plan for a solution to the problem; – not to be discouraged by bad luck and to convince you that diligence is important; – determination of ideas creativity based on results; – Pay attention to the formation of mental satisfaction from the result of creative activity. There are many possibilities for the use of sound recording tools in comparing language phenomena, comparing similarities and differences, and in the cultivation of speech. Sound recording can be done by both the teacher and the student. A student can read and write a text and hear it without an instructor in order to learn what his/her speech is like. Can quickly distinguish defects in speech during the hearing. Sound recording tools can be widely used in working with all sections of the language – phonetics, lexicology, orthoepy, phraseology, morphology, syntax, punctuation, methodology. Speech exercises with the help of a tape recorder are performed. The use of such methods develops listening, comprehension and speaking skills. The scientific and methodological literature on new pedagogical technology considers the originality of teaching methods. These methods are presented as innovative methods. Below we recommend some of the techniques that can be applied in education:- Cooperative teaching technology. This way not only does the learning tasks work together, but students are taught to study in cooperation. The process of cooperation, mutual assistance and exchange of ideas between students is established; - Technology of didactic games. In it, an active movement is organized in the lesson through the use of various didactic games. The lesson is lively, and students' interest grows; - Problem-Based Educational Technology. Creating problem situations, throwing problematic questions, organizing discussion aimed at solving a

problem situation and confirming the correctness of conclusions by the teacher;

- Check – test lessons. These are classes designed to test and test students' knowledge and skills, where test tasks and other forms of testing are organized.
- Collaboration across local and global networks. Information about changes in science and technology around the world, contacts with 14-year-olds from another country, access to necessary information in a data complex located on the territory of another country can be used in cooperation with Internet systems. Therefore, the introduction of the technology of training on the basis of the cooperative principle into the educational process is a requirement of the time. The teacher must thoroughly know the technology and be able to choose it correctly based on the specifics of the language materials being studied. The more often effective forms of tutoring are used, the higher the interest students will have in English subjects. Learning a language is a process that can last a life. Effective use of cooperative teaching technology will equip students to learn in cooperative learning. There will be a process of cooperation, mutual assistance and exchange of ideas between young people. To improve the quality and effectiveness of education, the study of foreign leading methods and the introduction of international standards is important. When studying the teaching methods of foreign countries, we will need to examine everything they do in the educational process. In the process of studying abroad, several foreign methodologies are conducted. These methodologies provide students with an understanding of the knowledge they have entered.

1. Active education. These methods follow students' activities and develop their skills of job management, problem solving, suggestions and advice. The student engages himself and learns to consolidate his past knowledge by applying it to new tasks.
2. Local education. This methodology is used to help students understand information related to the characteristics and history of a region or country in which they are located. Research works are carried out using local history, use of available resources (museums, Tashkents, archaeological sites), acquaintance of local culture, assistance and written libraries.
3. Cooperative education. In this way, group work, cooperation and mutual suggestion are very important. Students work in a group and help each other to gain additional knowledge. This method develops the student's physical, educational and social support.
4. Technological education. The widespread use of technology in America is very important in the educational process. Computers, tablets, internet, and other technological tools make the process of students understanding and learning knowledge even easier.
5. Vacation education. Vacation programs are one of the most modern

ways to learn students. Develops students' creativity through extracurricular peer and sporting activities. Test exercises are tasks to complete to learn a new topic. Mock exercises can be used in the following two ways: - Students are given several exercises within a new topic in order to encourage the students to grasp the self-awareness of the topic rather than the topic explained to the instructor. After completing these assignments and receiving feedback from the teacher about their mistakes, students will come up with a new topic on their own; - Or test assignments can be given after the teacher has explained a new topic, so that the concept can be put into practice and better understood. In the process of cooperation, it is desirable for the two subjects to act together, to be partners, to form an alliance with the older and more experienced with the inexperienced. Neither of them is necessarily superior to the other. Cooperation takes many forms: commonwealth, partnership, empathy, co-creation, co-governance. The cooperation solves problems related to the process of implementation of the national idea and is directly related to the restoration, development and implementation of advanced national moral values and criteria in our modern life, educational and educational process, and is divided into four areas: - human-personal approach; - didactic activating and developing complex; - the concept of education; - Improvement of environmental culture is expedient.

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